

Challenges Faced By LIS Professionals While Using New Media as a Tool for Providing Information to the Library Users during Pandemic Period

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Abstract

The challenging times of pandemic period affected whole world and provided an opportunity to change though forcefully. Amongst all, library services were needed for variety of reasons and thankfully the technological advancement came to rescue the field by offering a channel for dissipation of information amongst all the professionals. In view of the above the challenges faced by libraries of academic colleges affiliated Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati were studied. The data was generated using a structured questionnaire using survey method. All the statistical analysis of the data was carried out using SPSS 18.0 software. In view of the study results it was observed that lack of official/policy guidelines for use of new media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic was prevalent in majority of colleges. Furthermore, the data revealed that most of the LIS professionals of study area had favorable attitude towards use of new media during Covid-19. Amongst other aspects, infrastructure facilities, lack of funds, lack of adequate human resources, poor technical know-how about use of New Media for disseminating library services were the challenges faced by LIS professionals during Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: *Pandemic period, New Media, library services, infrastructure facilities, technical know-how*

Introduction:

The role of library as the power house of knowledge is well established all over the world. However, not all situations are conducive to seamless operation of library services. One such once in a lifetime situation occurred during the Covid-19 pandemic period, when almost all activities were negatively affected including the library services. Moreover, considering the importance of library services, many Library and Information Science (LIS) professionals made sincere attempts through various innovations to provide maximum services to their respective users. Also, many LIS professionals played a great role in attending to the information needs of the varied users. The pandemic period has completely turned the world upside-down disrupting the normal way of life. With the closing down of the educational institutions across the globe, the library patrons had faced great hardships as they were unable to access the library to meet their information requirements. Besides many aspects the pandemic has dramatically remodeled and transformed the education sector into a digital learning hub, wherein the role of LIS professionals has changed remarkably. The pandemic has given a wide range of opportunities for the librarians to upgrade their digital literacy skills in order to provide the finest services to the library users/patrons during the pandemic period.

During the pandemic period, academic libraries had to explore many options so that library users can get desired information. This is because; closure of academic activities necessitated most of

class to operate through online platforms. Libraries also had to shift to online mode to provide services to assist students with access to materials for assignments, selection and dissemination of information resources on various fields to researchers, virtual research help, virtual instruction, online reference services, access to e-books and e-journal, linking users to health institutions and organization on information relating to coronavirus, publish a pamphlet and handbills for safety measures against coronavirus. The technological advancements and innovations have transformed the traditional libraries to the present smart Libraries. However, this transformation is not uniform in the study area i.e. western Vidarbha region of Maharashtra and many academic libraries are left behind as they could not change their service delivery during the pandemic period. In view of the above, this investigation was carried out to assess challenges faced by LIS professionals while using New Media as a tool for providing information to the library users during pandemic period.

Research Methodology:

The present study is conducted by using a combination of descriptive and exploratory research design. In the study area, there are total 394 colleges are existing, which are affiliated to Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University (SGBAU), Amravati. Out of that 235 are academic colleges affiliated to the SGBAU, Amravati were selected for the Data Collection. The LIS professionals working in these colleges formed the samples. The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire and by following survey method. Prior to its use the

reliability and validity of the questionnaire was tested. Subsequently, secondary data was collected from different National and International Magazines, Journals, Books of the reputed authors, internet and other sources. Statistical analysis of the

data was carried out with the help of various statistical tests. The descriptive statistics, such as frequency, mode, percentage, etc were determined from the collected data. All the statistical analysis was carried out by using SPSS 18.0 Software.

Results and Discussion:

Guidelines for use of New Media by LIS professionals during Covid-19 pandemic:

Table 1: Availability of Official/Policy guidelines for use of New Media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic

Response	Nos.	Percentage
Available	16	6.8
Not available	166	70.6
Don't know	53	22.6
Total	235	100.0

Chi-square 156.027; **df:** 2, **p**<0.05; **Table Value:**5.99

Above **Table 1** presents results pertaining to availability of Official/Policy guidelines for use of New Media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic in the academic colleges of SGBAU. According to 6.8% respondents

official/policy guidelines were available for use of New media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic while 22.6% respondents were not aware about it. Further according to 70.6% respondents such guidelines were not available for use of New media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic.

Attitude towards use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic:

Table 2: Attitude of the LIS professionals towards use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic

Attitude	Nos.	Percentage
Favourable	138	58.7
Unfavorable	68	28.9
Indifferent	29	12.3
Total	235	100.0

Chi-square 78; **df:** 2, **p**<0.05; **Table Value:**5.99

Above **Table 2** shows information pertaining to attitude of LIS professionals of academic colleges of SGBAU towards use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic. 58.7%

respondents had favorable attitude towards use of new media during Covid-19 while 12.3% respondents had indifferent attitude. Further 28.9% respondents had unfavorable attitude towards use of new media during Covid-19.

Infrastructure facilities for use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic:

Table 3: Adequacy of infrastructure facilities for use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic

Response	Nos.	Percentage
Adequate	59	25.1
Inadequate	133	56.6
Not sure	43	18.3
Total	235	100.0

Chi-square 58.955; **df:** 2, **p**<0.05; **Table Value:**5.99

Above **Table 3** shows information pertaining to adequacy of infrastructure facilities in the academic colleges of SGBAU for use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic. According to

25.1% respondents infrastructure facilities were adequate for use of new media during Covid-19 while 18.3% respondents are not sure about it. Further 56.6% respondents feel that infrastructure facilities were not adequate for use of new media during Covid-19.

Technical know how about use of New Media for disseminating library services:

Table 4: Technical know how about use of New Media for disseminating library services

Response	Nos.	Percentage
Very good	27	11.5
Fair	66	28.1
Poor	142	60.4
Total	235	100.0

Chi-square 87.136; **df:** 2, **p**<0.05; **Table Value:**5.99

Above **Table 4** shows information pertaining to technical know-how among LIS professionals of academic colleges of SGBAU for use of New Media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic. 11.5% respondents had very good level of technical know-how about use of

New Media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic while 28.1% respondents had fair technical knowledge. Further 60.4% respondents had poor technical know-how about use of New Media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic.

Availability of funds to purchase latest technology tools:

Table 5: Availability of funds to purchase latest technology tools for disseminating library services

Response	Nos.	Percentage
Adequate	17	7.2
Not adequate	194	82.6
Not sure	24	10.2
Total	235	100.0

Chi-square 256.702; **df:** 2, **p**<0.05; **Table Value:**5.99

Above **Table 5** shows information pertaining to availability of funds in the academic colleges of SGBAU to purchase latest technology tools for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic. According to 7.2% respondents

funds were available to purchase latest technology tools for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic while 10.2% respondents are not sure about it. Further 82.6% respondents feel that funds were not available to purchase latest technology tools for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic.

Internet & power supply during Covid-19 pandemic period:

Table 6: Internet & power supply during Covid-19 pandemic period

Response	Nos.	Percentage
Good	184	78.3
Fair	40	17.0
Poor	11	4.7
Total	235	100.0

Chi-square 219.366; **df:** 2, **p**<0.05; **Table Value:**5.99

Above **Table 6** shows information pertaining to speed of internet & power supply in the academic colleges of SGBAU during Covid-19 pandemic. According to 78.3% respondents high

speed internet & power supply was available during Covid-19 pandemic while 17.0% respondents feel that it was of fair level. Further according to 4.7% respondents internet & power supply provided during Covid-19 pandemic was of poor level.

Availability of human resources:

Table 7: Availability of adequate human resources

Response	Nos.	Percentage
Adequate	37	15.7
Inadequate	191	81.3
Not sure	7	3.0
Total	235	100.0

Chi-square 249.022; **df:** 2, **p**<0.05; **Table Value:**5.99

Above **Table 7** shows information pertaining to availability of adequate human resources in the academic colleges of SGBAU during Covid-19 pandemic. According to 15.7%

respondents adequate human resources were available during Covid-19 pandemic while 3.0% respondents are not sure about it. Further according to 81.3% respondents adequate human resources were not available during Covid-19 pandemic.

Conclusions:

Guidelines for use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic

On the basis of the study results it is evident that most ($p < 0.05$) of the academic colleges of SGBAU do not have availability of official/policy guidelines

for use of New media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic.

Attitude towards use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic

In the backdrop of study results it is evident that most ($p < 0.05$) of the LIS professionals of academic

colleges of SGBAU had favorable attitude towards use of new media during Covid-19.

Infrastructure facilities for use of New Media during Covid-19 pandemic

On the basis of the study results it is evident that most ($p < 0.05$) of the academic colleges of SGBAU do not had adequate infrastructure facilities for use of new media during Covid-19.

Technical know how about use of New Media for disseminating library services

On the basis of the study results it is evident that most ($p < 0.05$) of the LIS professionals of academic colleges of SGBAU had poor technical know-how about use of New Media for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic.

Availability of funds to purchase latest technology tools

On the basis of the study results it is evident that most ($p < 0.05$) of the academic colleges of SGBAU do not had adequate funds to purchase latest technology for disseminating library services during Covid-19 pandemic.

Internet & power supply during Covid-19 pandemic period

On the basis of the study results it is evident that most ($p < 0.05$) of the academic colleges of SGBAU had good internet & power supply during Covid-19 pandemic.

Availability of human resources

On the basis of the study results it is evident that most ($p < 0.05$) of the academic colleges of SGBAU had inadequate human resources during Covid-19 pandemic.

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